

EFFECTS OF FRICTION ON THE MEASUREMENT OF THE MODE II INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: In this paper, analysis and experiments are conducted to investigate the effects of friction on the experimental evaluation of mode II interlaminar fracture toughness in the 4ENF (four-point bend end-notched flexure) and ONF (over notched flexure) tests. An analytical model based on a point friction model and classical beam theory is proposed to evaluate the effects of the friction between the crack faces under the loading point on the energy release rate of mode II interlaminar fracture. Explicit formulae for 4ENF and ONF tests are derived to evaluate the energy release rate including the effects of friction. The validity of the analytical model is recognized by the comparison with a finite element analysis. Experiments of mode II interlaminar fracture of CFRP T800/#3631 unidirectional laminate based on ENF (end notched flexure), ELS (end loaded split), 4ENF and ONF tests are conducted to confirm the analytical and numerical evaluations. Experimental results reveal that the analytical model can give a rational accuracy in the evaluation of the effects of friction. The effect of friction in the 4ENF test is lower than that in the ONF test. Hence, The 4ENF testing method is considered as a good testing method for the experimental evaluation of Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness including the initial and propagation values.

KEYWORDS: friction, analytical model, mode II fracture, interlaminar toughness, test methods

INTRODUCTION

The interlaminar fracture is an important failure mode for composite laminates. The optimal design and material selection of composite structures need an accurate evaluation of the interlaminar fracture toughness of composite laminates. The DCB testing method has been used widely to evaluate the Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness [1,2]. In contrast, the experimental evaluation of the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness is not as successful as that of Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness. The ENF test [2,3] commonly used for determining the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness has a crucial drawback that only one initial data per specimen can be obtained because the crack growth is unstable. No complete resistance curve (R-curve) can be obtained. In order to overcome the instability of conventional ENF test, a stabilized ENF test [4,5] has been proposed based on a control system of COD (crack opening displacement) of ENF specimen. Another widely used test is ELS test [6]. The stabilized ENF test and ELS test can obtain not only the initial value but also the whole R-curve from one specimen. However, The stabilized ENF test needs an additional COD control system and the ELS test needs a complex loading fixture. These requirements limit the application of these two testing methods to only few laboratories.

To find a way out of the situation, two new testing methods of 4ENF [7] and ONF [8] have been proposed in recent years. These two new testing methods are as simple as conventional ENF testing method. The crack growth is stable under displacement control and then the whole R-curve can be easily obtained from one specimen. It is expected that the same value would be obtained from each of 4ENF, ONF and ENF tests. However, it is not so easy to achieve the same values as expected. One problem is that the loading point is over the crack faces in the cases of 4ENF and ONF tests, which is different from the case of ENF test. It is considered that the friction between the crack faces under loading point might influence the experimental evaluation of the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness. In recent studies [9-11] it has been reported that the 4ENF test produced toughness much higher than those obtained from ENF test, whereas the studies [12,13] indicate that the 4ENF and ENF tests give essentially the same toughness based on the accurate measurement of compliance and

crack length. In the finite element study of the reference [12], it was found that the 4ENF test produces toughness 5% or less higher than those from ENF test due to the effects of friction. It was indicated that the frictional effects are not large enough to fully account for the error in interlaminar fracture toughness obtained by ENF and 4ENF tests. In the reference [13], the inaccurate measurements of crack length and compliance during the 4ENF test are considered as the major reason for the deference in interlaminar fracture toughness obtained by ENF and 4ENF tests. In contrast, no more study on the ONF test can be found, although it is also a simple and stable test method. Therefore, it is still an open problem that how the friction between the crack faces under loading point influences the experimental evaluation of the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness in 4ENF and ONF tests directly or indirectly.

In this paper, analytical, numerical and experimental efforts are made to investigate the effects of friction on the experimental evaluation of mode II interlaminar fracture toughness in the 4ENF and ONF tests. An analytical model based on a point friction model and classical beam theory is proposed to evaluate the energy release rate of mode II interlaminar fracture including the frictional effects. Explicit and simple formulae are derived to calculate the energy release rates. A finite element analysis is conducted to verify the validity of the analytical model. Experiments of mode II interlaminar fracture of CFRP T800/#3631 unidirectional laminate based on ENF, ELS, 4ENF and ONF tests are conducted to observe the effects of friction on the measurement of interlaminar fracture toughness and to confirm the analytical and numerical evaluations.

ANALYTICAL MODEL

Consider the 4ENF and ONF tests illustrated in Fig. 1. The ONF can be considered as a modified three point bend with the loading point out of the center of the beam. It is obvious that frictional contact occur at the loading points, the supporting points, and the crack faces over the supporting point and under the loading point. The frictional effects at loading points, supporting points and crack faces over the supporting point can be easily removed by inserting a teflon film into the contact locations. However, it is difficult to remove the frictional effects at the crack faces under the loading point. Hence, the frictional effects between the crack faces under the loading point should be estimated during the experimental evaluation of the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness.

It is assumed that the beam is linear elastic, the longitudinal modulus of the beam is E_L , and that the width of the beam is B . According to the linear elastic-fracture theory without frictional effects, the energy release rate can be expressed by

$$G_{II} = \frac{1}{B} \frac{dU}{da} \quad (1)$$

where U is the strain energy and a is the crack length.

If the effects of friction at the crack faces are not considered, it is easy to obtain the expression of the strain energy U based on the classical beam theory. However, it is difficult to obtain the exact expression of U with the frictional effects because of the complexity of frictional contact behavior during the crack growth. Here, an approximate analytical model is proposed. Consider a point friction model as described in Fig. 2. The friction contact occurred between the crack faces is considered as one point friction contact problem. Then, the effects of the frictional forces F on the beam deformation can be considered to be equivalent to those of an axis force N_F and a moment M_F acted on the upper and lower half-beam respectively. The axis force N_F and the moment M_F in 4ENF and ONF tests can be easily obtained as follows based on the beam theory.

$$N_F = \frac{P}{4} \mu, \quad M_F = -\frac{P}{8} \mu H, \quad (\text{for 4ENF test}) \quad (2)$$

(a) 4ENF(four point bend ENF)

(b) ONF (over notched flexure)

(a) A point friction model

(b) Effects of frictional forces

Fig. 2 An analytical model for the frictional effects at the crack faces (for ONF test)

where μ is the friction coefficient and H is the half-thickness of beam. Referring to the energy method of the classical beam theory, the strain energy U including the frictional effects can be expressed by

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{2L} \left[\frac{M(x)^2}{E_L(x)I(x)} + \frac{N(x)^2}{E_L(x)A(x)} \right] dx \quad (4)$$

where $M(x)$, $N(x)$ are moment and axis force, respectively, $I(x)$ is the moment of inertia of the cross-sectional area, and $A(x)$ is the cross-sectional area. Then, referring to Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, the strain energy induced by external load and frictional force in the case of 4ENF test can be written as

$$U_{4ENF} = \int_0^s \frac{1}{E_L I_H} \left(\frac{Px}{4} \right)^2 dx + \int_s^a \frac{1}{E_L I_H} \left(\frac{Ps}{4} - \frac{1}{2} FH \right)^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_a^{s+2l} \frac{1}{E_L I_{2H}} \left(\frac{Ps}{2} \right)^2 dx \\ + \frac{1}{2} \int_{s+2l}^{2L} \frac{1}{E_L I_{2H}} \left[\frac{P}{2} (2L-x) \right]^2 dx + \int_s^a \frac{F^2}{E_L BH} dx \quad (5)$$

where

$$F = \frac{P}{4} \mu, \quad L = s + l, \quad I_H = \frac{BH^3}{12}, \quad I_{2H} = 8I_H \quad (6)$$

Integrating equation (5) and inserting it into equation (1), one can obtain

$$G_{II(4ENF)} = \frac{9P^2 s^2}{16E_L B^2 H^3} \left(1 - \frac{2\mu H}{3s} + \frac{4\mu^2 H^2}{9s^2} \right) \quad (7)$$

Referring to Fig.1(b) and similar to the case of 4ENF, the strain energy induced by external load and frictional force in the case of ONF test can be written as

$$U_{ONF} = \int_0^s \frac{1}{E_L I_H} \left(\frac{2L-s}{4L} Px \right)^2 dx + \int_s^a \frac{1}{E_L I_H} \left(\frac{Ps}{2} - \frac{1}{2} FH - \frac{Psx}{4L} \right)^2 dx \\ + \frac{1}{2} \int_a^{2L} \frac{1}{E_L I_{2H}} \left[Ps \left(1 - \frac{x}{2L} \right) \right]^2 dx + \int_s^a \frac{F^2}{E_L BH} dx \quad (8)$$

where

$$F = \frac{P}{2} \mu, \quad I_H = \frac{BH^3}{12}, \quad I_{2H} = 8I_H \quad (9)$$

Integrating equation (8) and inserting it into equation (1), one can obtain

$$G_{II(ONF)} = \frac{9P^2 s^2 (2L-a)^2}{16E_L B^2 H^3 L^2} \left[1 - \frac{4\mu H}{3s(1-a/2L)^2} + \frac{13\mu^2 H^2}{36s^2(1-a/2L)^2} + \frac{2\mu Ha}{3Ls(1-a/2L)^2} \right] \quad (10)$$

From equations of (7) and (10), one can easily calculate the effects of friction on the energy release rate for 4ENF and ONF tests. Numerical examples for $L=50$ mm, $s=25$ mm, $B=25$ mm, $H=1.5$ mm, $E_L = 154.6$ GPa are shown in Fig. 3. The load P is selected as 746 N for 4ENF test and 532.9 N for ONF test, when the energy release rate for crack length $a=30$ mm is equal to 600 (N/m) for both of 4ENF and ONF tests. These results reveal that the energy release rate decreases with the effects of friction by 1 to 2 % for 4ENF case and 3 to 6 % for ONF case from $\mu = 0.25$ to $\mu = 0.5$. Hence, it is recognized that the effects of friction on the energy release rate in the 4ENF case is very small compared with that in the case of ONF case.

Fig. 3 Energy release rate with effects of friction between crack faces based on the beam theory and a point friction model.

Fig. 4 Plane strain finite element calculation model. A small inserter of $0.1 \text{ mm} \times 0.1 \text{ mm}$ is placed between the crack faces over the support point to avoid simulate the experimental situation. The material constants of the composite beam are

$$E_L = 154.6 \text{ GPa}, \nu = 0.3$$

and the material constants of the steel inserter are

$$E = 210 \text{ GPa}, \nu = 0.3$$

The friction coefficient between the inserter and the crack face is assumed to be zero. The load P is 29.84 N for 4ENF case and 21.32 for ONF case to produce an energy release rate of 600 (N/m) without frictional effects. A commercial code of ABAQUS is used to conduct the finite element analysis. The numerical results are shown in Fig. 5. The results of finite element analysis show that the energy release rate decreases with the effects of friction by 2 to 4.5 % for 4ENF case and 3 to 8 % for ONF case from $\mu = 0.25$ to $\mu = 0.5$. The results for 4ENF case are similar to those reported in [12]. Comparing with Fig. 3, these results for the friction effects are larger than those obtained by the analytical model. However, the analytical model is considered to be useful because it give explicit and simple formulae for the calculation of the energy release rate including the frictional effects.

Similarly, the finite element analysis also reveals that the frictional effects on the energy release rate are small in 4ENF case and relatively large in ONF case.

EXPERIMENTAL

Both of the above theoretical analysis and the finite element analysis reveal that the frictional effects between the crack faces under load point on the mode II interlaminar fracture are small in 4ENF test and relatively large in ONF test. In order confirm these results, experimental research is conducted. For the sake of comparison, the conventional ENF test and modified ELS test are also performed.

The specimen is made by T800/#3631 carbon/epoxy unidirectional composite with 24 plies. The initial crack is made by inserting a 12.5 μm Kapton film into the mid-plane of the laminate. The specimen is straight-sided, 140 mm long, 25 mm wide, and nearly 3.3 mm thick. The testing length ($2L$) is 100 mm for ENF, 4ENF and ONF tests, and 90 mm for ELS test. The side edge is painted white and scaled to observe the crack growth. An optical system with a microscope, a CCD camera

and a video camera (not shown) measure the crack length. Before ELS (end-loaded split) a crack of about 2 mm is made for specimens. The testing procedure of loading, unloading and reloading is adopted. Figure 6 illustrates the ENF and ELS tests. For the ENF and ONF tests, a rigidly clamped end is employed to replace the roll-supporting end in the standard ELS test. The fracture toughness characterized by the critical energy release rate is determined from following formulae based on the conventional compliance method.

In the case of ENF test, the critical energy release rate [2] is determined from

$$G_{II(ENF)} = \frac{9a_1^2 P_C^2 C_1}{2B(2L^3 + 3a_1^3)}, \quad a_1 = \left[\frac{C_1}{C_0} a_0^3 + \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{C_1}{C_0} - 1 \right) L^3 \right]^{1/3}, \quad (11)$$

where the a_0 , a_1 are the initial crack length and the critical crack length, C_0 , C_1 are the initial compliance and the compliance at the critical load, respectively. P_C is the critical load, which is generally determined by maximum load or 5% offset load according to the load-displacement curve.

In the cases of ELS, 4ENF and ONF tests, the conventional compliance method is used to obtain the critical energy release rates.

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{P_C^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (12)$$

where C is the compliance,

$$C_{(ELS)} = \alpha_0 a^3 + \alpha_1 \quad (13)$$

$$C_{(4ENF)} = \alpha_0 a + \alpha_1 \quad (14)$$

$$C_{(ONF)} = \alpha_0(a - 2L)^3 + \alpha_1 \quad (15)$$

α_0 , α_1 are constants which are determined from experimental compliance calibration data.

Tests are conducted by using a MTS testing system. Five specimens are tested for each kind of ENF, ELS, 4ENF and ONF tests. The following Fig. 7 shows the typical load displacement curves. From these load displacement curves, it is seen that a nearly constant critical load is needed to make the crack grow in 4ENF test and that an increasing load is needed to make the crack grow. These facts reveal that the crack growth in 4ENF and ONF is more stable than that in ELS and ENF tests. Furthermore, it is observed that the hysteretic loops are larger in 4ENF and ONF tests than those in ELS test. These hysteretic loops are considered to be due to the effects of friction between the crack faces under the loading point. In ENF, ELS and 4ENF tests, the critical load is determined from the maximum load or the 5% offset load. However, this method to determine the critical load is invalid in the ONF test. Hence, the load at nonlinear point is taken as the critical load in ONF test. Furthermore, the compliance is calculated from the slope of the load displacement curve for all the tests.

Experimental results are described in Fig. 8. The results obtained from the ENF test are given in the left one of upper Fig. 8, which represent the initial mode II interlaminar fracture toughness. The difference among the values from five specimens is relatively small. The average of five specimens is 593.33 (N/m). The right one of upper Fig. 8 shows the resistance curve obtained from the ELS test. The average of the initial fracture toughness is a little higher than the one of ENF test. This may be due to the effects of clamped constraint at the right because the clamped end constrains the horizontal movement of the specimen. The average of the propagation toughness of five specimens varies slowly

friction between the crack faces under the loading point has little influences on the experimental

evaluation of the fracture toughness. This fact confirms that the predictions of the theoretical and FEM numerical analysis are appropriate. The right one of lower Fig. 8 shows the results obtained from ONF test. The initial fracture toughness is a few larger than the one obtained from ENF test, and the propagation toughness increases with the crack growing. These results reveal that the effects of

Fig. 8 Critical energy release rates obtained from ENF, ELS, 4ENF and ONF tests

friction between the crack faces under the loading point on the crack front. The determination of fracture toughness is large (a) Nonlinear elastic model which is considered. (b) Linear elastic model which is considered. The theoretical and FEM numerical analysis.

From above Fig. 9 Illustration of effects of friction on the load displacement curve. It is large in ONF test. Hence, it is considered that the 4ENF test is appropriate for the experimental evaluation of mode II interlaminar fracture toughness. Then, a question is that why the previous researches [9-11] reported quite different results. In order to clarify this issue, let us refer the typical load displacement curve obtained from 4ENF test again. It is observed that there are obvious hysteric loops and that the loading curve appears a little nonlinear. Figure 9 illustrates the effects of friction on the load displacement curve and two models to determine the compliance in 4ENF test. It is seen that the determination of the compliance based on the slope depicted in the nonlinear elastic model might give a good approximation to the accurate the critical energy release rate, whereas the determination of the compliance based on the slope depicted in the linear elastic model might give relatively large difference from the accurate critical energy release rate. For instance, if the linear elastic model is applied in the calculation of the compliance, the critical energy release rate will be over 20% larger

than the results shown in the 4ENF case of Fig. 8. Thus, it is pointed out that the determination of the compliance based on the slope of the load displacement curve is quite important for the accurate estimation of the critical energy release rate in 4ENF case. This point was also indicated in a previous paper [13].

CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed an analytical model to estimate the effects of friction between crack faces under the loading point on the experimental evaluation of mode II interlaminar fracture toughness. The results of finite element analysis prove that the theoretical model is simple and valid. Experimental results reveal that the effects of friction on the experimental evaluation of fracture toughness are small if the determination of the compliance is determined from the slope of the load displacement curve. Thus, the testing procedure of load, unload and reload is necessary to obtain relatively accurate results. A linear elastic model might induce large error in the evaluation of the fracture toughness.

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